

EFFECT OF EMPLOYEE COMMITMENT ON ORGANIZATIONAL PERFORMANCE AT AFGHANISTAN INTERNATIONAL BANK (AIB)**Abdul Baset Ayoubi**

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ABSTRACT

This study was conducted to assess the effect of employee commitment on the performance of the Afghanistan international Bank. This study examined three dimensions of commitment: affective commitment, continuation commitment, and normative commitment. The relationships between these types of commitment and organizational performance were the primary focus of the study's objectives. The purpose of this investigation was to assess the impact of employee commitment on Afghanistan International Bank's (AIB) operational effectiveness. A survey of 250 (AIB) workers from different departments and levels of the company's hierarchy was done using a quantitative research method. The research investigation will prioritize the identification of the appropriate sample size, target population, selection methodology, and data collection instruments to guarantee the credibility and dependability of the findings. The process of data analysis encompassed several types of methodologies, such as factor analysis to uncover the latent factors that underlie the observed correlations among variables, correlation analysis to ascertain the associations between the variables under investigation, and regression analysis to achieve the study's objectives by evaluating the effects between variables. Conclusions Draw a Statistically Significant Link among the Affective Commitment, Continuity, and Normative Commitment, impact of 59.3%, 63.9%, and 70.4%, respectively on the performance of employees at the International Bank of Afghanistan. Therefore, that statement has been supported by the study's findings.

Keywords:

International bank of Afghanistan (AIB), Employee commitment, Organization performance, Productivity, profitability

INTRODUCTION

Organizational success has been measured since ancient times (Brudan, 2009), and modern organizations and the rise of empirical management practices have made it easier for these activities to be used as management practices. Even though the public and private sectors need to do more with less (Dixit & Bhatti, 2018), there seems to be a global organizational performance problem. (Ameeq & Hanif, 2019) This problem is common in developing, emerging, and industrialized countries, and it has made it more important to have good ways to judge how well groups are doing. Performance is done and given as a very important way to help them work at a certain level. In Europe, the first known organizational performance measurement model, called the Tableau de Bord, was made by process engineers in France in the 1930s. They were trying to improve production by learning more about how causes and effects work together. (Tezza, Bornia, and Vey, 2010) States like the United States have created performance measures for their businesses, especially for the performance of the government sector, which is needed to make the tools for performance management.

1.1 Background of study

Meyer and Allen (1991, 1997, and Lee and Chen (2019) all say that employees can show their commitment in different ways. Even though many of the models that have been made to explain these differences have a lot in common, there are also big gaps between them. For our purposes, we focus on the three-part approach that Meyer and Allen (1991, 1997) came up with. Who showed that staff commitment is real, long-lasting, and the norm? Affective commitment is the mental bond that makes a worker desire to stay with a company. This

commitment happens when a person feels emotionally connected to the group, identifies with it, and gets more involved with it. Mathotaarachchi (2018) says that affective commitment is the emotional bond between an employee and the company. This is because they don't have any other options and don't get paid enough to leave the company. Continuance commitment is a person's decision to stay with a company because of the time and resources they have already put into it and the cost of switching jobs (Umoh, 2019).

Afghanistan is one of the countries, where companies, particularly banks, continue to function at a low standard. The success of the public institutions is still restricted, particularly when it comes to the provision of services, the fulfillment of operational deadlines, and the optimization of their financial resources. According to Ogbé (2019), Afghanistan is one of the countries where it is extremely challenging for the government to carry out its responsibilities, particularly in terms of the provision of services. If you want to improve the way that public sector organizations work and the services that they deliver, it is essential to place the appropriate amount of emphasis on organizational performance.

Globally, employee dedication is crucial. In today's highly competitive marketplace, every business encounter new obstacle when it comes to maintaining efficiency and cultivating a dedicated workforce. (2016) Dixit and Bhati in light of this, it is essential to comprehend what dedication entails and what outcomes are conceivable. Employees who arrive to work every day and perform their duties independently are no longer sufficient. In order to demonstrate their value, employees must now work collaboratively and think like enterprises. According to Maugo (2017), a company's most valuable competitive advantage is its personnel. People management is an integral element of how a business operates. This is due to the fact that human resources and the organization itself are the same entity. Typically, a well-managed business views the regular employee as the primary source of productivity gains. (2017, Dost & Ahmed) These companies believe that their employees, rather than their capital, are the most essential aspect of their business and contribute to its growth.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Banks are aware of the need to attain enhanced performance of the bank through profitability, operational costs, and efficiency of the organizations. The bank, like any other financial institution, is established to attain efficiency in their operations and increase flexibility for the purposes of attaining financial excellence. Contrary to the notion of attaining improved performance, banks in Afghanistan have experienced challenges in its profitability, for example, the bank profits reduced from 2016 to 2020 by close to 1.5% (Central bank of Afghanistan, 2019). The banks experienced an increase in operational costs by close to 21% in 2020 and 2021 and the profits reduced from 2018 in 10.1% to 9.2% in 2021. There has been reduced efficiency in the operations through reduction in the customer satisfaction that has affected bank sales (Qais and Boris, 2018). The performance dimensions of the banks have highly affected the way in which the banks operate reduced efficiency and operations capacities (Tahiri, 2018). The management of the bank tried to develop mechanisms to ensure performance, but the performance of the banks remained low. The bank report of 2018 had indicated low employee commitment amongst the employees, could it be this that is responsible for the performance constraints at the bank, Because of this, a study was conducted at the International Bank of Afghanistan to determine the influence that employee dedication had on the performance of the bank is significant to address the status quo.

1.3 Hypothesis of the Study

H01: There is a statically significant effect of affective commitment on organizational performance at Afghanistan International Bank.

H02: There is a statically significant effect of continuance commitment on organizational performance at Afghanistan International Bank.

H03: There is a statically significant effect of Normative commitment on organizational performance at Afghanistan International Bank

1.4 Research Significant

The findings of this study will be beneficial to policymakers because they will provide pertinent recommendations for the improvement of normative employee commitment, which administrators will use to maximize employee productivity for the organization's success. The study will evaluate the relationship between

affective commitment and the organizational performance of the bank, as well as the effect that affective commitment has on organizational performance. The findings of the study will aid policymakers in designing and formulating effective normative commitment principles that will direct organizations in enhancing their relationships with their employees. The study will expand the scholarly community's knowledge and literature on how employee commitment (three dimensions) can effectively and successfully support their employees, thereby enhancing performance.

1.5 Theoretical Framework

A theoretical framework illustrating the link between employee commitment (IV) and the organization's performance (DV).

Source: Adopted from Mayer and Allen (1997) and Modified by the researcher
Figure 1.1: Conceptual Framework Showing Relationship between Employee Commitment and Organizational Performance

LITRATURE REVIEW

2.1 Theoretical Review

Howard Becker came up with Becker's side bet theory in 1960. This study was based on that theory. This method says that employee commitment has a big effect on how well an organization does its job. Becker's theory says the employee-company relationship is characterized by an "economic exchange contract" that outlines how exchanges of value take place. Committed employees demonstrate commitment in three distinct ways, emotionally, persistently, and socially. This is because they have made hidden investments, or "side-bets," by staying with a certain company. If someone left, it could be hard to get "side-bet" payments back. The word "side-bets" refers to the investments that a person makes. Becker argued in 1960 that, over time, people pay costs that make it harder for them to give up a consistent pattern of behavior, such as staying a member of a group.

According to Becker's theory, there is a direct connection between how dedicated workers are to the company's mission and how well it's carried out. As a matter of fact, assessments show that increased organizational performance is a reliable predictor of high levels of employee engagement. How long it lasts, and how prevalent it is. This claim was confirmed to be accurate by research conducted after Becker's idea was published. According to the findings of this research, the level of commitment exhibited by an individual should be

evaluated based on whether or not that individual would leave the group. Becker's argument that there is a close tie among employee commitment and organizational success inspired the majority of later notions of commitment with affectively, persistently, and normatively. The side-bet theory was thrown out as the primary theory of commitment, and Becker's theory was thrown out as the main theory of commitment. As a result, commitment became the primary behavior that should drive improvements in organizational performance. The evidence shown in Meyer and Allen's (1991) Commitment Scale, which may also be referred to as the commitment, demonstrates that the side-bet strategy had an influence on it. In 1960, Becker put forth the notion that a person is said to have made a commitment when they used a side bet as a means of connecting their other interests to a continuous plan of action.

2.2 Conceptual Review

2.2.1 Employee commitment

The degree to which workers remain with an organization and take the organization's goals seriously is what Marthis and Jackson (2000) call "employee commitment." According to Luthans (2006), employee commitment exists when workers put aside their criticisms of the company in order to remain a part of it. Employee commitment is a distinct indicator of the authority of employee empathy, as measured by the organization's objectives and morale, and the extent to which the employee remains involved in it. Employee commitment can also serve as an improved indicator for organizations that wish to remain in their current position or change. Allen and Meyer (1990) classified employee commitment as affective, ongoing, and normative.

According to Sang (2016), employee commitment is characterized by a steadfast belief and approval of a corporation's goals and principles, a willingness to apply substantial effort on the best interest of the organization, as well as a strong desire to keep their membership in the group. (Kibi go, 2016) Employee commitment is a symbol of connection to the organization. It also determines whether an individual will maintain or terminate a contract with an organization.

2.2.2 Organizational Performance

According to Cooper-Hakim and Viswesvaran (2015), the definition of organizational performance can be summed up and refers to a method of turning inputs into outputs with the aim of achieving specific objectives. Through results, we can see how the minimum cost relates to the actual cost (economy), how the actual cost relates to the actual output (efficiency), and how the actual output relates to the actual result (effectiveness). is demonstrated through performance. Regarding the conveyed information, success provides us with the following insights. performance provides this information. The degree to which an organization's objectives are met, such as meeting both short-term and long-term goals as and when they become due, is one way to evaluate the performance of an organization. White elephants are not something that should be funded with the limited resources that the organization has available. The most efficient use of resources ought to guarantee the highest possible production in the projects referred to in the organizational objectives. According to Wee (2009), companies simply do not have the luxury of throwing away their limited financial and skilled labor resources on endeavors that do not produce results.

Organizational performance is defined by Richard, Devinney, Yip, and Johnson (2009) as the degree to which an institution achieves its goals and objectives through the most efficient use of its resources (human, financial, and material). It refers to the process of converting inputs into outputs in a way that is both efficient and effective for the purpose of contributing to the well-being of society, the economy, and the environment.

2.3 Empirical Review

2.3.1 Relationship between Affective Commitment and performance

Research conducted on leasing companies in Sri Lanka, Bandula and Lakmini (2020) investigated the effect of affective employee commitment on job performance. A total of 115 employees from specialized Leasing companies (SLCs) and Licensed Finance Companies (LFCs) participated in the survey. The SPSS software program was used to look at the data, The research outcome is presented through the exhibition of primary and secondary research findings. The correlation between the level of employee commitment and their job performance was identified important finding. The observation showed that employee dedication influenced employee job performance, proving that employee dedication is substantially associated with one's level of

success in one's career. In addition, the data analysis demonstrates that employee dedication has a substantial impact on efficiency at work. Furthermore, according to this study, the aspect of employee commitment to job performance that is most influenced is continuation commitment. Whereas the author conducted a study in Sri Lanka, the current study will be conducted in Bank Afghanistan with a concentration on the factors influencing public sector commitment to address contextual gaps.

2.3.2 Relationship between Continuous Commitment and performance

As stated by Dixit and Bhati's (2018) research, when an individual who is employed by an organization is aware of the advantages of working for an organization, he or she remains committed. Before departing the organization, the employee should be aware of the actual costs of continuation commitment. According to Lew (2012), employees' performance is significantly enhanced by their commitment to continued improvement. Continuity commitment relating to staying with or leaving an organization. If a worker determines that the cost of departing an organization exceeds the benefits of remaining, he or she will decide to continue working for the organization rather than leaving it. Khan et al. (2013) posited that; the primary benefit of group membership is sustained commitment. Continuance commitment is determined by evident benefits and drawbacks. It requires the employee to weigh the advantages and disadvantages of departing the organization (Khan et al., 2013). Therefore, continuation commitment is regarded as calculative. It assesses the benefits of remaining and the negative consequences of quitting the institution.

2.3.3 Relationship between Normative Commitment and performance

Andrew (2017) investigated the connection between one's level of normative commitment and their level of job performance and discovered that there is a positive correlation among them. Their research indicated that, in an effort for advancement organizational performance, businesses must strengthen employee commitment to the organization. Mathotaarachchi (2018), conforming to the findings of Chen et al. (2006), emphasized that for an organization to attain success, it is imperative to have a significant degree of employee dedication in order to achieve long-term excellence in performance.

In 2017, Andrew conducted a study in the Eravurpatru Divisional Secretariat in the Batticaloa area of Sri Lanka. The purpose of this study was to examine the connection between emotive, continuous, and normative commitments and organizational effectiveness. The results show that the three commitments are linked to better organizational outcomes. The results show a significant relationship between the three independent variables and the efficiency of the organization.

3.0 METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

Mugenda and Mugenda (2003) point out that a research design is a plan for conducting a study that specifies how the various steps will be carried out so that the research problem can be solved instantly. A correlation research method was used for the study. The researcher used this type of study design because it is cheap and does not take a lot of time, and it gives a snapshot of a certain time. The expert also used quantitative methods to get information from the people who took part in the study. The statistical numbers that were given to the variables in the quantitative research method made it possible for the researcher to meet the goals of the study by looking at different thoughts and points of view (Kothari, 2004).

3.2 Populations and sample

According to Malhotra and Birks (2006), the researcher seeks information from a collection of elements or objects, which is referred to as the target population. The study population targeted are the employees of Afghanistan International bank. According to the Human resource report of 2021, the bank has 645 employees. The target population is hence this employee since they are part and partial of the bank and understand the study area. According to Yamane (1967), the minimum sample size is $n=247$.

3.3 Sampling Techniques

Sampling methodologies are employed to depict the attributes of the intended populace, thereby enabling the researcher to make a comprehensive inference about the entire population. The present study employed the stratified sampling method, which is classified as a probability sampling technique. The rationale for utilizing the probability sampling technique in this study is due to the presence of a well-defined sampling frame. Hence, it is possible to ascertain the probability of inclusion for each individual within the population. As per the

study's scope, individuals in clerical, non-clerical, junior, and apprenticeship positions were excluded from the analysis.

3.4 Data Collection Instrument (Questionnaire)

The utilization of questionnaires as a research instrument for the collection of primary data is a common practice. One such questionnaire is the five-point Likert scale structured question, which is designed to elicit essential data from respondents. The first section of the survey is designed to gather demographic and profile data from the participants. The second section is comprised of closed-ended questions that aim to collect data on independent and dependent variables.

3.5 Data Analysis Techniques

The information gathered from the participants will be inputted into a computer system and evaluated using the Statistical Packages for Social Scientists (SPSS) Version: 27. Descriptive statistics encompass measures such as frequencies, valid percentages, means, and standard deviation. The questionnaires included a summary of demographic characteristics of the respondents, as well as practices related to employee commitment and organization performance. The utilization of inferential statistics was employed to draw conclusions regarding the representativeness of the sample regression, by employing a straightforward regression analysis, this study set out to look at how employee dedication (the independent variable) correlates with organizational success (the dependent variable).

FINDINGS AND INTERPRETATION

This chapter outlines the findings of an investigation that was carried out to inspect the impact of employee commitment on the performance of the International Bank of Afghanistan (AIB). The present chapter is structured in accordance with the demographic characteristics of the participants, followed by an analysis that aligns with the research objectives presented in a systematic manner. The sub-chapters below exhibit the presentation, analysis, and interpretation of the data.

4.1 Demographic Respondents analysis

Table 4.1: Demographics respondents(n=250)

Categories		Frequency	Percent
Gender	Female	34	13.6
	Male	216	86.4
Age	18-30 Years	134	53.6
	30-50 years	79	31.6
	Above 50	37	14.8
	Years		
Education	High School	1	.4
	Bachelor's Degree	202	80.8
	Master's degree	47	18.8
Marital Status	Single	118	47.2
	Married	132	52.8
Total		250	100.0

Source: Primary data (IBM SPSS data analysis output) 2023

Table 4.1 findings regarding the demographic respondents, gender of respondents indicate that 216 (86.4%) respondents were male and only 34 (13.6%) were female. On the basis of the age of respondents, 124 (53.6%) respondents were between the ages of 18-30, 79 (31.6%) respondents were between the ages of 30-50, and 37 (14.4%) respondents were over the age of 50. On Education of respondents, there were 202 (80.8%) respondents with a bachelor's degree, 47 (18.8%) respondents with a master's degree, and 1 (0.4%) respondent with a high school diploma, indicating that respondents who were able to respond to the question items had sufficient understanding of the study. In terms of respondents' marital status, there were 132 (52.8%) married respondents and 118 (47.2%) unmarried respondents in the study.

4.2 Reliability of the Instrument

The Cronbach Alpha Coefficient test was utilized so that we could determine whether or not the study equipment was reliable. In particular, this examination examined the research items that were placed in order in the questionnaire.

Table 4.2: Reliability of the Instrument

	Cronbach's Alpha	N
Affective Commitment	.781	250
Continuance Commitment	.839	250
Normative Commitment	.858	250
Organization Performance	.938	250
Average	.854	

Source: Primary data (IBM SPSS data analysis output) 2023

The reliability of the instrument's internal consistency will be validated as the reliability test's mean was determined to be 0.854, which is significantly greater than the acceptable threshold of 0.70. Consequently, the examination was deemed to be credible.

4.3 Correlation Analysis

The goal of conducting correlation analysis is to assess the degree of association between the variables under investigation, thereby enabling the measurement of the relationship among them. A correlation analysis was conducted, having a significance value of less than 0.05. The study aimed to determine the how the factors are related to each other under investigation, and this formed the basis for interpretation.

Table 4.3: Correlation Analysis between Variables

		Correlations			
		Continuance commitment	Affective commitment	Normative commitment	Organization Performance
Continuance commitment	Pearson	1	.543**	.688**	.639**
	Correlation				
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000
	N	250	250	250	250
Affective commitment	Pearson	.543**	1	.791**	.593**
	Correlation				
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000
	N	250	250	250	250

Normative commitment	Pearson	.688**	.791**	1	.704**
	Correlation				
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000
	N	250	250	250	250
Organization Performance	Pearson	.639**	.593**	.704**	1
	Correlation				
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	
	N	250	250	250	250

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Primary data (IBM SPSS data analysis output) 2023

Table 4.3 examines the correlation between variables, The results had R-.639 and P= .000<0.05. The statistical analysis revealed that the P-value was below the 95% confidence interval, thereby indicating a significant association between continuance commitment and the performance of the International Bank of Afghanistan.

The results had R-.593 and, P= .000 <0.05. The statistical analysis revealed that the P-value was below the 95% confidence interval, indicating a significant correlation between the performance of the International Bank of Afghanistan and affective commitment.

The result had R.704 and P= .000 <0.05 The statistical analysis revealed that the P-value was lower than the established 95% confidence interval, suggesting a significant correlation between normative commitment and the performance of the International Bank of Afghanistan.

4.4 Regression Analysis

To achieve the study's objectives, the researcher aimed to establish the relationship between the variables under investigation. The present study involved a simple regression analysis to examine the impact of affective, continuance, and normative commitments on the performance of the International Bank of Afghanistan.

Table 4.4: Effect of Affective Commitment and organizational performance at international bank of Afghanistan

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.593 ^a	.352	.350	.30438

a. Predictors: (Constant), Affective commitment

ANOVA^a

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	
1	Regression	12.490	1	12.490	134.809	.000 ^b
	Residual	22.977	248	.093		
	Total	35.467	249			

a. Dependent Variable: Organization Performance

b. Predictors: (Constant), Affective commitment

Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
1	(Constant)	1.188	.247		4.801	.000
	Affective commitment	.628	.054	.593	11.611	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Organization Performance

Source: Primary data (IBM SPSS data analysis output) 2023

Table 4.4, results had, R-value of 0.593, indicating that affective commitment has a 59.3% impact on the performance of the (AIB). The findings of the study had an estimated standard error of .30438, indicating that the data obtained was substantially related to the findings.

The ANOVA results table, the F-value was 134.809, which is generally high, and the p-value was .000, which is less than the 95% confidence interval, indicating that affective commitment is statistically associated with international bank of Afghanistan's performance.

On the coefficients of determination, the p-values for affective commitment and organizational performance of the (AIB) were 0.000 and 0.000, respectively, exceeding the 95% confidence interval required to determine the significance level. Since there was a statistically significant effect of affective commitment on organizational performance at the International Bank of Afghanistan, thereby first hypothesis is taken as accepted.

Table 4.5: Effect of Continuance Commitment and organizational performance at international bank of Afghanistan

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.639 ^a	.409	.407	.29075

a. Predictors: (Constant), Continuance commitment

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	14.502	1	14.502	171.551	.000 ^b
	Residual	20.965	248	.085		
	Total	35.467	249			

a. Dependent Variable: Organization Performance

b. Predictors: (Constant), Continuance commitment

Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
1	(Constant)	.575	.266		2.160	.032

Continuance commitment	.872	.067	.639	13.098	.000
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a. Dependent Variable: Organization Performance

Source: Primary data (IBM SPSS data analysis output) 2023

Table 4.5, results had R-value of 0.639, indicating that the continuance commitment has a 63.9% impact on the performance of the (AIB), The findings of the study had an estimated standard error of.29075, indicating that the data obtained was substantially related to the findings, according to the study.

The ANOVA results table indicates the effect of continuance commitment on international bank of Afghanistan's organizational performance; the F-value was 171.551, which is generally high, the p-value was.000, which is less than the 95% confidence interval, indicating that continuance commitment is statistically related to international bank of Afghanistan's performance.

On the coefficients of determination, the p-values for continuance commitment and organizational performance were 0.000 and 0.032, respectively; these p-values were above the 95% confidence interval required to determine the significance level. The results of the findings indicate that a commitment to continuity has a statistically significant effect on the performance of the (AIB), Thereby second hypothesis is taken as accepted/Supported.

Table 4.6: Effect of Normative Commitment and organizational performance at international bank of Afghanistan

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.704 ^a	.495	.493	.26865

a. Predictors: (Constant), Normative commitment

ANOVA^a

	Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	17.568	1	17.568	243.424	.000 ^b
	Residual	17.899	248	.072		
	Total	35.467	249			

a. Dependent Variable: Organization Performance

b. Predictors: (Constant), Normative commitment

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Coefficients Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.083	.191		5.671	.000
	Normative commitment	.723	.046	.704	15.602	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Organization Performance

Source: Primary data (IBM SPSS data analysis output) 2023

Table 4.6 The findings result had R-value of .704, indicating that normative commitment has a 70.4% impact on the performance of the international bank of Afghanistan. The findings of the study had an estimated standard error of .26865, indicating that the data obtained was substantially related to the findings.

The ANOVA table, F-value was 243.424, which is generally high, and the p-value was .000, which is less than the 95% confidence interval, indicating that normative commitment has a statistically significant relationship with international bank of Afghanistan's performance.

On the coefficients of determination, findings were provided regarding the effect of normative commitment and organization performance based on the (AIB). The P-values for normative commitment and organization performance were 0.000 and 0.000, respectively, exceeding the 95% confidence interval required to determine the significance level. The study's findings indicate that normative commitment has a statistically significant impact on the performance of the (AIB). The third hypothesis is accepted.

H₀₁: There is a statistically significant effect of affective commitment on organizational performance at international bank of Afghanistan. (ACCEPTED)

H₀₂: There is a statistically significant effect of continuance commitment on organizational performance at international bank of Afghanistan. (ACCEPTED)

H₀₃: There is a statistically significant effect of normative commitment and organizational performance at international bank of Afghanistan. (ACCEPTED)

IN SUMMARY AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Conclusion

The findings regarding the first objective indicate that affective commitment has a 59.3% impact on the performance of the (AIB). The F-value was 134.809, which is generally high, and the p-value was .000, which is less than the 95% confidence interval, indicating that affective commitment is statistically associated with international bank of Afghanistan's performance. Thus, the first hypothesis is accepted.

The findings regarding the second objective indicate that continuance commitment has a 63.9% impact on the performance of the (AIB). The F-value was, 171.551 which is generally high, and the p-value was .000, which is less than the 95% confidence interval, indicating that continuance commitment is statistically associated with international bank of Afghanistan's performance. Therefore, the second hypothesis is accepted.

The findings regarding the third objective indicate that normative commitment has a 70.4% impact on the performance of the (AIB). The F-value was 243.424 which is generally high, and the p-value was .000, which is less than the 95% confidence interval, indicating that normative commitment is statistically associated with international bank of Afghanistan's performance. Thus, the third hypothesis is accepted.

5.2 Recommendations

H1: Effect of Affective commitment on Organization performance at (AIB).

A recommendation based on these findings would be to prioritize initiatives and strategies that promote and enhance affective employee commitment. Fostering a positive work environment, promoting an effective organizational culture, recognizing, and rewarding employee contributions, and offering opportunities for personal and professional development can all contribute to enhancing affective commitment.

H2: Effect of continuance commitment on Organization performance at (AIB).

According to the findings, continuance commitment plays a vital role. Thus, to leverage this relationship and improve performance, it could be advantageous to concentrate on strategies that promote and strengthen employee loyalty, and this may involve providing incentives for long-term commitment, providing opportunities for career advancement, and nurturing a positive work environment that encourages employee loyalty and commitment.

H3: Effect of Normative commitment on Organization performance at (AIB).

Based on these findings, the recommendation is to focus actions that improve and strengthen normative commitment among (AIB) staff. Consider techniques include fostering a strong organizational culture that promotes shared values and a feeling of purpose to encourage normative commitment. Encourage staff involvement and participation in decision-making processes to develop a feeling of ownership and commitment to the bank's vision and goals. Furthermore, create chances for workers to contribute to the community or society, since this can boost their feeling of duty toward the firm.

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